

Studies on the Ternary Complexes of Vanadium(V) with N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl N'-o-chlorophenyl-p-Toluidine Hydrochloride and Thiocyanate

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A spectrophotometric method for the determination of vanadium(V) based on the synergic extraction of ternary complex of vanadium with N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-o-chlorophenyl-p-toluidine hydrochloride (abbreviated as HPCPTH) and thiocyanate is reported. A 1:2:2 (metal : HPCPTH:SCN⁻) green complex in acidic medium is formed which can be extracted in chloroform. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration of metal from 0.6–6.8 ppm. The molar absorptivity of the complex at 590–600 nm is about 6350 ± 501 mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and the Sandell's sensitivity is 0.008 μg of vanadium per cm⁻². The present method is simple, rapid and highly selective and most of the common ions including Mn²⁺, Cr³⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, Mo⁶⁺ do not interfere. The applicability of this method has been tested by analysing three B.C.S. steels for vanadium.

N-hydroxy-N,N' diaryl benzamidines are reported as versatile reagents for carrying out determination of a large number of transition metal ions¹⁻⁵. The newly synthesised hydroxyamidine-HPCPTH, mono-basic and bidentate chelating agent reacts with vanadate ion giving blue-violet 1:2 complex having a flat peak in the region 550-580 nm. The addition of thiocyanate to this complex was found to produce a bathochromic shift in the wavelength of maximum absorption and a marked increase in the molar absorptivity. On the basis of the strong synergistic effect of thiocyanate and high molar absorptivity of the complex formed, a simple, rapid, sensitive and selective method is proposed for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) at microgram levels. The present method is superior to established methods⁶⁻¹².

Experimental

Apparatus : A Carlzeiss specord ultra-violet visible spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm. quartz and silica cuvettes was employed for recording the spectra. For all absorbance measurements an ECIL/VIS spectrophotometer model GS-865 was employed. The pH values of the solutions were measured with a systronic pH meter type-322.

Reagents : All the reagents used were of analytical purity.

A stock solution of ammonium meta vanadate was prepared by dissolving in doubly distilled water and standardised volumetrically using potassium permanganate¹³. From this stock solution, a solution containing 20 μg vanadium(V) ml⁻¹ was prepared.

N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-o-chlorophenyl-p-toluidine hydrochloride was prepared following the method of Deb and Mishra¹⁴. The resulting hydrochloride was recrystallised from absolute ethanol. m.p. 168°, yield-75%. The compound gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

A 0.1% W/V solution of HPCPTH in chloroform was employed for extraction work. 5% aqueous potassium thiocyanate solution was used throughout the experiment.

Procedure : An aliquot of ammonium meta vanadate solution containing 100 μg of vanadium(V) is mixed with 2 ml of 5% potassium thiocyanate solution in a 100 ml separatory funnel. The total aqueous phase is made upto 25 ml. The pH of the solution is adjusted by dilute hydrochloric acid. Add 15 ml of reagent solution in chloroform and extract for 2 min, separate the coloured chloroform layer containing the vanadium(V) complex and collect over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a beaker. Extract the aqueous phase with 2×4 ml portions of chloroform. Transfer the combined extracts in 25 ml volumetric flask and dilute to volume with chloroform and measure the absorbance at λ_{max} of the complex.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The absorption spectra of vanadium(V)-HPCPTH-complexes in the absence and presence of thiocyanate are shown in figure 1. The vanadium(V)-HPCPTH complex shows a flat peak between 550-580 nm with molar absorbance 764 1.mole⁻¹cm⁻¹. In the presence of thiocyanate a stable

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Fig. 1. Absorption spectra

- (A) (—●—●—●—●—●—) V(V)-HPCPTH-SCN⁻
 (B) (—○—○—○—○—○—) V(V)-HPCPTH
 (C) (—●—●—●—●—●—) 0.1% W/V HPCPTH in chloroform.

1:2 green adduct is formed with molar absorptivity of about $6350 \pm 50 \text{ l.mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 600 nm. A strong synergistic effect is observed as shown by the hyper and bathochromic shift on adduct formation.

Choice of solvent: Various water-insoluble organic solvents were tried. Benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform, all extracted the ternary complex. Chloroform proved to be most satisfactory because it gives high distribution ratio for the reagent and ternary complex.

Effect of variables: The optimum pH range is 0.8-3.0. Maximum absorption is reached when HPCPTH and thiocyanate concentration are 6 and 8 times that of vanadium respectively. Excess HPCPTH and thiocyanate cause no adverse effect on the λ_{max} and the absorbance value of the coloured system. The order of addition of reagents was not critical.

No adverse effect was noted on the absorbance of the coloured system when the ionic strength of the aqueous phase was adjusted between the 1-3 M potassium or sodium chloride. 2 min. was sufficient for complete extraction. The complex was stable for at least 30 hr. at $27 \pm 2^\circ$.

Beer's law, optimum concentration range, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and precision:

The system obeys Beer's law within the concentration range of 0.6-8.0 ppm of vanadium(V). The effective working range from the Ringbom Plot¹⁵⁻¹⁶ was found to be 1-5.8 ppm of vanadium(V). The sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.008 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ at 600 nm with molar absorptivity $6350 \pm 50 \text{ l.mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. The

precision of the method has been checked by measuring the absorbance of 10 samples, each containing a final concentration of 4 ppm of vanadium(V). The mean absorbance was 0.50 with standard deviation 2.3×10^{-3} .

Composition: The composition of vanadium(V): HPCPTH:SCN⁻ was determined by mole ratio¹⁷, Job's method¹⁸ and slope ratio¹⁹ method. The result obtained showed the formation of 1:2:2 (metal:reagent:thiocyanate) mixed complex in chloroform.

Effect of Diverse ions: Many foreign ions were tested for interference with 4 ppm of vanadium(V) at 2.0 ± 0.5 pH. The interference due to Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} could be eliminated by masking with trisodium phosphate and thiourea respectively. Chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, thiosulphate, urea, thiourea, phthalate, borate, citrate, lanthanoid, tartrate, alkali and alkaline-earth metals did not interfere.

The tolerance limit for other ions are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF 4 PPM VANADIUM(V) AT 2.0 ± 0.5 pH

Ions added	Tolerated* amount ppm	Ions added	Tolerated* amount ppm
Fe^{2+}	1000 ^a	Ti^{4+}	250
Co^{2+}	400	Mo^{6+}	150
Ni^{2+}	600	W^{6+}	10
Cu^{2+}	1600 ^b	Al^{3+}	900
Zn^{2+}	1000	Cr^{3+}	600
Cd^{2+}	1200	Th^{4+}	800
Mn^{2+}	600	Nb^{5+}	80
Be^{2+}	1500	Ta^{5+}	200
Zr^{4+}	150	F^-	500
Bi^{5+}	800	AsO_4^{3-}	400
U^{6+}	500	SeO_4^{2-}	800

* causing 2% error

^a In presence of trisodium phosphate

^b In presence of thiourea

Determination of vanadium in steel samples:

Steel samples containing upto 3 mg. of vanadium were dissolved in 40% nitric acid. Tungsten was removed as hydrated tungstic oxide by filtration. The filtrate was made upto 250 ml with distilled water and vanadium was determined by the procedure described above. Results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(V) IN BCS* STEELS

Steel	Found ^f %	Certified value	Standard deviation
64a Alloy steel	1.56	1.57	0.0084
241/1 High speed steel	1.55	1.57	0.014
252 Low alloy steel	0.45	0.46	0.0070

* British Chemical Standard Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, Yorks.

^f Mean of five results

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